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Inquiry Based Teaching in Writing Classroom: the Effectiveness to the Students' Creativity

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Abstract: The main objectives of the research are to find out whether (1) Inquiry Based Teaching is more effective than Guided Writing to teach writing skill; (2) Students having high creativity have better writing skill than those having low creativity; and (3) there is any interaction between teaching methods and students' creativity in teaching writing skill for students. The research applied in this research was an experimental research. The teaching methods are Inquiry Based Teaching and Guided Writing. Creativity as the attributive variable was divided into high creativity and low creativity. The population of the research was the students of junior high school consisting of 176 students. The samples of this research were the class 8B as experimental class and 8A as control class that consisted of 22 students in each class. The result of data analysis shows that; (1) Inquiry Based Teaching is more effective than Guided Writing to teach writing skill; (2) Students having high creativity have better writing skill than those having low creativity; and (3) There is an interaction between teaching methods and students' creativity to teach writing skill for the students. Based on the research findings, it can be concluded that Inquiry Based Teaching is an effective method to teach writing skill, and the effectiveness is affected by the degree of students' creativity

Keywords: *Inquiry Based Teaching, Guided Writing, writing skill, creativity, experimental research*

INTRODUCTION

One of the aims of teaching English for junior high school students in Indonesia is to develop communicative competence in oral and written form to achieve the functional literacy level. Based on the competence standard, there are three scopes for English subject in junior high school, two of them are (a) the ability in discourse, it is the ability to comprehend and/or to produce oral text and/or written that realized in the integrated-four language skills to achieve the functional literacy level; (b) the ability to comprehend and to create various short functional texts, monologue and essay in the form of procedure, descriptive, recount, narrative and report. The gradation of the material appears in using the vocabularies, language order and rhetoric steps. Therefore, writing skill is also important to be taught for junior high school students.

Byrne (1997: 1) states that writing is the act of forming letters or combination of letters; making marks on a flat surface of some kinds. It is more than the production of graphic symbols, just as speech which is more than the production of sounds. The symbols have to be arranged according to certain conventions to form words, and words have to be arranged to form sentences. Writing is putting words into sentences and sentences into paragraphs, spelling words correctly, punctuating and capitalizing in customary ways, and observing conventions in written form.

Writing is also one of the most difficult skills to master in both first language and a second language. According to Byrne (1997: 4-5), there are three factors that cause difficulties in writing. They are (1) Psychological problems. Writing is essentially a solitary activity. The persons are required to write their own ideas, without the possibility of interaction or benefit of feedback, so it makes the act of writing difficult in itself. It is different from speaking in which it presents feedback from the other; (2) Linguistic Problems. The writers have linguistic problems, such as the choice of sentence structure, how the sentences are linked together and sequence. Different from speaking, it is normally spontaneous and there is little time to pay attention either to organize the sentence structure or for connecting the sentences. In other words,

incomplete and even ungrammatical utterances can be tolerated. While in writing, they cannot be tolerated; (3) Cognitive Problems. Learning to write is not similar to learning to speak. Learning to speak grows up in normal circumstances that spend much in doing it. Speaking appears without much conscious effort or thought and generally the person talks because they want to know about matters which are of interest or relevant to them socially or professionally. On the other hand, writing is learnt through a process of instruction. The writers also have to learn how to organize their own ideas in such a way that those ideas can be understood by a reader who is not present and perhaps by a reader who is not known to us.

The success of teaching writing is influenced by some factors. The first, it is influenced by the methods. Teaching methods are needed in teaching learning process, especially in teaching writing. Method is specific instructional design or system based on a particular theory of language learning; it contains detailed specifications of content, roles of teacher and learners, and teaching procedures and techniques (Richard and Rodger, 2001: 245). The teacher should be selective to use the appropriate method to teach. A method is very useful for teachers in their work to transfer knowledge to their students. Students also need teaching method as a tool to receive knowledge from their teacher.

Related to the importance of teaching method in teaching and learning above, this research aims to investigate the effectiveness of two teaching methods, Inquiry Based Teaching (IBT) and Guided Writing in teaching writing and also one of the psychological aspects, creativity. Inquiry Based Teaching (IBT) is chosen because one of the methods suggested in 2013 curriculum is Inquiry Based Teaching (IBT). Guided Writing is chosen because it is the method that the teacher usually used in her teaching writing of English.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In principle, Inquiry Based Teaching (IBT) is a method that focuses on ‘how we know what we know’ (evidence). Because Inquiry is something that the students do, not

something that is done to them (Inquiry and the National Science Education Standard (in Stewart & Rivera, 1998: 4), so Inquiry Based Teaching emphasizes on the process of learning (why we understand something), how deep we understand something rather than how much knowledge we possess. Inquiry Based Teaching also places the teacher as facilitator of learning (Stewart & Rivera, 1998: 4). In other words, teacher's role on Inquiry Based Teaching learning is as facilitator. Transferring knowledge is done indirectly. Students are seen as a teacher partner in searching knowledge. It is in line with Stewart & Rivera statement; Student's role is as active, independent learner (investigator) (1998: 4). From the explanation above it can be assumed that Inquiry Based Teaching is not a method that centralizes on teacher but on students.

In contrast with Inquiry Based teaching, Guided Writing is a teaching method in which the teacher demonstrates the process of writing a sentence or a paragraph using proper English convention such as a particular aspects of text type, grammar, punctuation or spelling, provides the model texts and helps the class to prepare the written work, either through written or oral assistance (Simpson, 1998: 1). Students are then given opportunities to apply the skills through independent writing. This method is teacher-centered method. So, the student will be too dependent on their teacher. It will make them not to be creative students.

Besides methods, the success of teaching writing is also influenced by the students' creativity. The level of the students' creativity is different among the students. In the case of teaching writing, the differences of students' creativity will affect the teaching methods used to teach writing. Creativity means being able to come up with your own clever ideas. Creativity is ideas that one has and uses them to do or create something. It is a mental and social process involving the generation of new ideas or concepts or new associations of the creative mind between existing ideas or concepts. The student's creativity in writing also influences the student's capability in writing skill. The higher creativity will make the students have higher capability in writing skill.

Based on the background above, the writer formulates the problems in the form of research questions as follows: (1) Is Inquiry Based Teaching more effective than Guided Writing to teach writing?; (2) Do the students who have high creativity have better writing skill than those who have low creativity?; (3) Is there any interaction between teaching methods and students' creativity to?

Writing is the mental and physical act of forming letters and words, but it is much more than that, it is putting words into sentences, sentences into paragraphs, spelling word correctly, punctuating and capitalizing in customary ways, and observing conventions in written forms and more. Writing is not solely the product of an individual, but is a social and cultural act (Weigle, 2002: 19)

According to Harmer (2004: 16), writing is a productive skill. Productive skill can be defined as producing a sequence which is arranged in a certain order and linked together in certain ways. The sequence may be very short-perhaps only two or three sentences and they form a coherent whole which is called a text (Byrne, 1997: 17). Writing is not a spontaneous skill or acquired easily, in fact, it is viewed as probably the most difficult thing to do in language (Nunan, 1999: 271). Furthermore, he states that writing is a complex, cognitive process that requires sustained intellectual effort over a considerable period of time (Nunan, 1999: 273).

Huges (1996: 91) states aspects of writing are; (1) Grammar, that is an element of writing which deals with a set of rules to have a writer constructs sentences that make sense and acceptable in English, (2) vocabulary, it deals with a list of words and their meanings, (3) mechanics, that is the convention in writing that is related to punctuation, spelling, and capitalization; (4) fluency, which refers to the ease and style of the composition; and (5) organization, that is the logical sequence and cohesion or the flow of ideas being put into written language to make unified contribution to the whole paragraph.

Inquiry Based Teaching is a range of philosophical, curricular and pedagogical method to teaching. Inquiry based teaching is a pedagogical approach that invites students to explore academic content by posing, investigating and answering questions (Sweetland; 2008: 1). Furthermore, Warner & Mayers (2011: 1) state that Inquiry-based teaching is a teaching method that combines the curiosity of students and the scientific method to enhance the development of critical thinking skills while learning. The worlds of inquiry, curiosity, and wonder should be alive in classrooms everywhere.

The essence of inquiry based teaching is the learning environment to facilitate students centered instruction and give sufficient guidance to ensure direction and success in discovering concept and principle. Teacher uses questioning in order to help students to understand them. Sund and Trowbridge (1993: 110) state that one way to help students to do it is by questioning. They also explain that the orientation of an inquiry based teaching is that the teacher seldom tells, but he/she often questions. In other word it needs teacher's capability to design question. This is so because by asking questions, the teacher assists the students in using their mind. Teachers acts as facilitators of learning, not those who always give information or instruction to their students and teach as if they are single source of knowledge. They motivate the students to ask questions and solve the problem independently; nevertheless, it is possible to do these in pairs or group.

Ontario (2005: 51) defines guided writing as a method that gives students the opportunity to review a recently taught writing skill in a small-group setting and then to apply the skill through independent writing. Guided writing lesson is a method in which the teacher demonstrates students the process of writing sentence or paragraph using proper English conventions then students given opportunities to use these strategies in their own work (Simpson, 1998: 1). Guided writing in further step of controlled writing as Raimes stated as guided composition is a prolongation of controlled composition that less controlled than the examples of controlled composition and it gives students some but not all of the content they will use (Raimes, 1983: 103).

Additionally, Reid (1993: 25) states that guided writing is free writing limited to structuring sentences, often in direct answer to question, the result of which looked like a short piece of discourse, usually a paragraph. Moreover, the exercises are language-based, they are usually concentrated on vocabulary building, reading comprehension, grammar, and even oral skills that culminate in a piece of writing. Meanwhile, Lan, Hung, & Hsu (2011: 149) show that guided writing strategy is to provide instructional materials or relevant media to help students in writing.

According to Boden (1995: 2), creativity is natural language. It means that creative language is an unending source of novel sentences. But these sentences are novelties which clearly could have happened before, being generated by the same rules that can generate other sentences in the language. Any native speaker could produce novel sentences using the relevant grammar. Munandar (2009: 68) states that creativity is as a process that manifests itself in fluency, in flexibility as well as in originality of thinking.

METHODOLOGY

This research was conducted at one of junior high schools in Karanganyar. This research is categorized as an experimental research. This experimental research is aimed at observing whether there is an interaction between teaching methods and students' creativity in teaching writing. There are two kinds of variables in this research: independent and dependent variables. Independent variables are Inquiry Based Teaching implemented in experimental group and Guided Writing implemented in control group. The dependent variable is writing skill and creativity is a moderator variable. Each group is classified into two different levels of creativity: high and low. A factorial design was used to analyze the main effects for both experimental variables as well as an analysis of the interaction between treatments. This research used a simple factorial design 2x2, which was aimed at describing and proving the influence of Inquiry Based Teaching and Guided writing in teaching writing viewed from students' creativity.

In this research, the population was the eighth grade students who are divided into eight classes. Each class consists of 22 students. The whole students were 176 students.

Sample is a part of all representatives of a population that is analyzed. A sample is the group from which information is obtained (Fraenkel and Wallen, 2009: 90). The sample should represent the population since the research result will be generalized to the population. Sample might be defined as a set of elements taken from a larger population according to certain rules. In other word, it can be said that sample is representative elements from a larger population taken using certain rules.

The researcher used cluster random sampling in which every class or unit had an equal chance of being selected from the frame or list. In this research, the researcher intended to take cluster random sampling in getting two classes. All of the classes had similar chance. The researcher made eight lotteries that represented the class, A-H. After that, the researcher picked two lotteries randomly. Then, the researcher got two classes, class A and Class B. Then, the researcher made lottery again to determine the experimental class and the control class. The experimental class was taught using Inquiry Based Teaching while the control class was taught by using Guided Writing. Finally, the researcher got class A as the control class and class B as the experimental class.

There were two main instruments of test in this research, namely writing test and creativity test. Furthermore, the writing test was used to identify the students' writing skill after being given treatment. The researcher conducted written test which evaluated these aspects: content, organization, vocabulary, language use (grammar), and mechanics. Before administering the test, the researcher should firstly check the readability of the instrument using questionnaire.

In administering a test, it was important to set and to determine an understandable instruction. Related to the readability, the instruction of the test was then tested to some students to know whether it was readable or not. Unreadable instructions were not effective and did not function as they were supposed to. To check the readability of instruction, it was tried out to some respondents. Before administering a test to the students, the researcher should firstly check the readability of instrument. Dubay (2004:

3) defines readability as the ease understanding or comprehension due to the style of writing. The test could be said that it was successful if the students could understand it, read it at an optimum speed, and found it interesting. In other word, the instruction of the test should be clear and easy to understand. To know the readability of the writing test, the researcher, firstly, asked the students who were not the members of experimental or control group to read and understand the instruction of the writing test. If 80% students understood the test, so it could be concluded that the test was readable.

To identify the students' creativity, the students were given the creativity test which used verbal creativity test from Munandar. A creativity test originally uses simple tests of divergent thinking and other problem-solving skills, which are scored on four scales: fluency, flexibility, originality, and elaboration. They involved subtest of creativity test consisting of word initials, word creations, sentence formulation from three letters, similar characteristics, extraordinary uses of words, and consequences or effects (Munandar, 2012: 68). Before the test is used in this research, it was tried out to identify the readability. The aim of it was to identify whether the instrument was understandable or not.

The data of students was analyzed by using descriptive analysis and inferential analysis. Descriptive analysis was used to know the mean, median, mode, and standard deviation of the score of test, inferential analysis was used to know the normality and the homogeneity of the data. The normality and homogeneity test were done before testing the hypothesis using ANOVA test.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

1. RESULT

The normality of the data that consists of columns, rows and cells can be stated normal if L_o is lower than L_t at the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$. The result of normality test can be seen at table 1

No	Data	No of Sample	L_o	L_t	α	Status
1	The class treated using Inquiry Based Teaching (A_1)	22	0.1769	0.190	0.05	Normal
2	The class treated using Guided Writing (A_2)	22	0.1247	0.190	0.05	Normal
3	The students having high creativity (B_1)	22	0.0965	0.190	0.05	Normal
4	The students having low creativity (B_2)	22	0.0960	0.190	0.05	Normal
5	The students having high creativity taught using Inquiry Based Teaching (A_1B_1)	11	0.1389	0.249	0.05	Normal
6	The students having low creativity taught using Inquiry Based Teaching (A_1B_2)	11	0.2273	0.249	0.05	Normal
7	The students having high creativity taught using Guided Writing (A_2B_1)	11	0.1558	0.249	0.05	Normal
8	The students having low creativity taught using Guided Writing (A_2B_2)	11	0.1281	0.249	0.05	Normal

Table 1. The Result of Normality Test

Based on the table above, the value of L_o from the data A_1 , A_2 , B_1 , B_2 , A_1B_1 , A_1B_2 , A_2B_1 , A_2B_2 are lower than L_t at level significance $\alpha = 0.05$ ($L_o < L_t$). Therefore, it can be assumed that the samples are in normal distribution. After analyzing the normality, researcher did the next test that was homogeneity test. Homogeneity test was conducted in order to know whether the data obtained from students' writing scores were homogeny or not. The result of students' homogeneity test can be seen at table 2.

	1	2	3	4
ΣX	990	891	934	910
ΣX^2	89144	72213	79412	75348
Si^2	4.40	4.20	10.69	6.62
s^2	6.48			
$\text{Log } s^2$	0.81			
B	32.46			
$\text{LN}10$	2.3026			
χ_o^2	2.97			
χ_t^2	7.81			

Sample	Df	1/(df)	Si^2	$\text{Log } si^2$	(df)Log si^2
1	10	0.1	4.40	0.64	6.43
2	10	0.1	4.20	0.62	6.23
3	10	0.1	10.69	1.03	10.29
4	10	0.1	6.62	0.82	8.21
Σ	40				31.16

Table 2. The Result of Homogeneity Test

Based on the computation result above, it can be seen that χ_o^2 (2.97) is lower than χ_t^2 with the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ (7,81) or $\chi_o^2 < \chi_t^2$ (2.97 < 7,81). Therefore, it can be stated that the data are homogenous. After finding out the normality and homogeneity test, researcher did a further test in order to test the hypothesis using ANOVA test. The result of ANOVA test can be seen in table 3.

Source of Variance	SS	Df	MS	F _o	F _t (0,05)
Between Columns	29,4545	1	29,4545	4,53147	4,09
Between Rows	338,273	1	338,273	52,042	
Column by Row (Interaction)	124,455	1	124,455	19,1469	
Between Group	492,182	3	164,061		
Within Group	260	40	6,5		
Total	752,182	43			

Table 3. The Result of 2x2 Multifactor Analysis of Variance Test

After analyzing the hypothesis test, the researcher presented the summary of mean scores. It can be seen at table 4.

	A1	A2	
B1	89,91	84,91	87,41
B2	81	82,72	81,86
	85,45	83,82	

Table 4. Mean Scores

Based on the table above, it can be concluded that: (1) Because F_o (4,53147) is higher than F_t with the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ (4.09), H_o is rejected and the difference between column is significant. Thus, it can be concluded that Inquiry Based Teaching significantly differs from Guided writing to teach writing to the eighth grade students. In addition, the mean score of students taught using Inquiry Based Teaching (85,45) is higher than that those taught using Guided Writing (83,82). Therefore, it can be summed up that Inquiry Based Teaching is more effective than Guided Writing; (2) Because F_o (52,042) is higher than F_t with the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ (4.09), H_o

is rejected and the difference between rows is significant. It can be concluded that students having high creativity (87,41) is also higher than that of those having low creativity (81,86). Therefore, it can be concluded that students having high creativity have better skill in writing than those having low creativity; (3) Because F_o interaction (19,1469) is higher than F_t with the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ (4.09), H_o is rejected and there is an interaction between the teaching method and the students' creativity to teach writing to the eighth grade students.

The last step that the researcher did was to compare the means of every treatment with the other means by using Tukey test. The result of Tukey test can be seen at table 5.

Between Group	q_o	q_t	Status
A1 - A2	3.010	2.950	Significant
B1 - B2	10.202	2.950	Significant
A1B1 - A2B1	9.199	3.110	Significant
A1B2 - A2 B2	3.178	3.110	Significant

Table 5. The result of Tukey Test

From table 5, it can be stated that;

1. Because q_o between columns (3.010) is higher than q_t with the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ (2.950), applying Inquiry Based Teaching significantly differs from Guided Writing. Because the mean of A_1 (85,45) is higher than A_2 (83,82), it can be concluded that Inquiry Based Teaching is more effective than Guided Writing to teach writing.
2. Because q_o between rows (10.202) is higher than q_t with the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ (2.950), it can be concluded that the students having high creativity and those having low creativity are significantly different in their writing skill. Because the mean of B_1 (87,41) is higher than B_2 (81,86), it can be concluded that the students having high creativity have better writing skill than those having low creativity.
3. Because q_o between cells A_1B_1 and A_2B_1 (9.199) is higher than q_t with the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ (3.110), applying Inquiry Based Teaching significantly

differs from Guided Writing to teach writing to the students having high creativity. H_0 is rejected and Inquiry Based Teaching significantly differs from Guided Writing to teach writing to the students having high creativity. Because the mean score of students having high creativity who were taught using Inquiry Based Teaching A_1B_1 (89,91) is higher than those having high creativity who were taught using Guided Writing A_2B_1 (84,91), it can be concluded that Inquiry Based Teaching is more effective than Guided Writing to teach writing to the students having high creativity.

4. Because q_0 between cells A_1B_2 and A_2B_2 (3.178) is higher than q_t with the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ (3.110), implementing Inquiry Based Teaching significantly differs from Guided Writing to teach writing to the students having low creativity. H_0 is rejected and Guided Writing significantly differs from Inquiry Based Teaching to teach writing to the students having low creativity. Because the mean score of students having low creativity who were taught using Inquiry Based Teaching A_1B_2 (81) is lower than those having low creativity who were taught using Guided Writing A_2B_2 (82,72). Therefore, it can be concluded that Guided Writing is more effectively used to teach writing to the students having low creativity than Inquiry Based Teaching.

Based on the result of the findings of number 3 and 4 of the Tuckey test, it is obviously found that Inquiry Based Teaching is more effective than Guided Writing to teach writing to the students having high creativity. Conversely, Guided writing is more effective than Inquiry Based Teaching to teach writing to the students having low creativity. Therefore, it can be concluded there is interaction between teaching methods and students' creativity. In addition, the effectiveness of the teaching methods depends on the level of the students' creativity.

2. DISCUSSION

Teaching writing using Inquiry Based Teaching is more effective than teaching writing using Guided Writing. The result of hypothesis testing shows that there is significant difference on the students' writing skill between the students taught using

Inquiry Based Teaching and those taught using Guided Writing because the finding of ANOVA shows that F_0 between columns (4,53147) is higher than F_t at the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ (4.09). Moreover, the finding of mean score between the students taught using Inquiry Based Teaching (85,45) is higher than the students taught using Guided Writing (83,82).

Inquiry Based Teaching is one of teaching methods to teach language skills which one of them is writing. Inquiry based teaching is a student-centered method. It fosters the teaching system centralizing the learning on the learners, while the teacher plays roles as the facilitator and feedback provider. Inquiry-based teaching is a method in which the process of constructing understanding is by questioning in which the students and the teacher share responsibility for learning and they collaborate on constructing new knowledge. This method can be used to teach writing in the English teaching and learning process.

Warner & Mayers (2011: 1) state that Inquiry-based teaching is a teaching method that combines the curiosity of students and the scientific method to enhance the development of critical thinking skills while learning. In applying inquiry-based teaching, the students are involved in their learning to formulate questions, investigate widely, and then build new understandings, meanings and knowledge. The students formulate the question to generate and develop their idea before doing their writing. The question can be posed by the teacher or the students. Sund and Trowbridge (1993: 110) state that one way to help students to do it is by questioning. Then the students can investigate the questions to find the answers. They can do it by having discussion with their group, sharing, and gathering information from any resources. This aims to help the students generating and organizing their ideas. After the students collect the information, they can make it as their draft of writing. Then they can start their writing. After finishing their writing, they revise and edit it with their friends from another group. The students present their writing in front of the class and the teacher and the students give feed back to the writing that is presented. So, it is a student-centered method in which teaching learning process focuses on the students. The teacher's tasks are facilitating and guiding the students to solve the problems and answering the question.

Meanwhile, guided writing is one of methods to help the students learn to write a composition. In applying guided writing in the class, it has weaknesses which make the process of teaching does not get maximum result. One of them is time consuming because the teacher should guide, help, and monitor every student. Through Guided Writing the students only imitate the model of text. Besides that, the students who do not have knowledge and information before cannot follow the guidance of the teacher and will be a passive in the class and they cannot write a text freely and individually.

It is supported by Gibson (2013: 5), guided writing is only temporary a small-group teaching that a group of students most need to practice with immediate guidance from teacher. He also adds that young and poor writers have limited control of methods in writing. It means they cannot follow the guidance of the teacher if they do not have knowledge and information before, so they cannot solve the problem in writing. Hyland (2003: 4-5) adds that the emphasis of teaching writing using Guided Writing is the students imitate the text model. By imitating the model, this not only hinders students from developing their writing beyond a few sentences, but can also mislead or confuse them when they have to write in other situation. From the statements above and the result of the research; it can be concluded that Inquiry Based Teaching is more effective than Guided Writing in teaching writing skill.

The students who have high creativity have better writing skill that those having low creativity. The result of the second hypothesis testing shows that there is significant difference on the students' writing skill between those who have high creativity and those who have low creativity because the finding of ANOVA shows that F_0 between rows (52,042) is higher than F_t at the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ (4.09). Moreover, the finding of mean score between students having high creativity (87,41) is higher than the mean score of students having low creativity (81,86).

Creative individuals have a great deal of energy. This great deal of energy makes them energetic and always ready to do everything. They will see any kinds of things, including the difficult one, as challenges to conquer. They like challenges and enjoy every single activity. They like to explore their ideas and imagination and to think freely. Furthermore, students with high creativity have a combination of playfulness, discipline,

and also responsibility. They like to alternate between imagination and fantasy at one end, and rooted sense of reality at the other. This kind of characteristics, in the end, leads the students who have high creativity to get better writing score since they have better flexibility, fluency, and originality of thinking which are important in producing a piece of writing.

On the other hand, the students with low level of creativity will just write what he sees, reads, and listens without being able to think what is beyond. They are unable to come up with their own fresh ideas and opinions when learning. In classroom activity, students with low creativity tend to be passive because they like something simple and being guided by the teacher so they cannot do anything in complex. These are some of the reasons why their writing scores are less than those having high creativity. Their low creativity makes them unable to express their ideas into written form better.

Csikszentmihalyi (1996: 58-73) states that students with low creativity tend to be passive. They do any kinds of tasks only based on the instruction given and do not really like if they are asked to think beyond what is given. In addition, they will be reluctant to do activities which require them to think creatively. They like something simple and like being guided. Students with low creativity usually do not really like activities because they like simple, guided, and straightforward activities which in turns make the teacher should control them intensively.

From the elaboration above and the result of the research, it can be concluded that the students who have high creativity get a better result in writing score than those who have low creativity.

Based on the finding of hypothesis testing, there is interaction between teaching methods and students' creativity on the students' writing skill. The result of ANOVA shows that F_0 columns by rows (19,1469) is higher than F_t (4.09). The finding of test shows that the mean score between students having high creativity taught using Inquiry Based Teaching (89,91) is higher than those taught using Guided Writing (84.91); and the mean score of students having low creativity taught using Inquiry Based Teaching (81.00) is lower than those taught using Guided Writing (82.72). It means that for

students who have high creativity, Inquiry Based Teaching is better method to teach writing than Guided Writing.

Inquiry based Teaching is a teaching method to develop the students' ability through their curiosity by asking and finding the answers. Inquiry Based Teaching emphasizes on the use of students' critical thinking to formulate questions and answer them independently. In inquiry-based teaching, the teacher's tasks are facilitating and guiding the students to solve the problems and answer the questions. The students are involved in their learning to formulate questions, investigate widely, and then build new understandings, meanings, and knowledge.

This method can help the students in generating and developing their idea before doing writing. The students who have high creativity can think deeply how to make a good written text. They can also share their ideas in writing the text together or separately through the process of writing, editing another's work, and peer reviewing. It is clear that inquiry based teaching is student centered. The students who have high creativity can be seen from their ability to produce or create something new and solve the solution when they face problems in writing. Because of the activities in inquiry-based teaching is rather complex, so Inquiry Based Teaching is more effective to teach writing for students with high creativity.

Meanwhile, Guided Writing emphasizes on teaching and learning process on teacher-centered. The students will be provided some information by the teacher in writing process. The teacher controls everything in the class. The students have to accept what the teacher gives passively. The students who have low creativity will just write what they see, read, and listen without being able to think what is beyond. They are unable to come up with their own fresh ideas and opinions when learning. They are unable to produce many ideas fluently, produce various points of view in solving problems, and produce unusual responses.

Based on Sternberg and Williams' opinion (1996: 11), students who are less creative often make mistakes in encouraging ideas and solution. Therefore, the students who have low creativity will be more suitable to be taught by using guided writing because students who have low creativity have some difficulties in composing the

project of writing. Besides, the students do not need to think hard because the teacher has prepared them with the models to follow. Every activity has been guided by the teacher in which students do not need to think creatively. So, it can be concluded that Guided Writing is more effective for students with low creativity.

Based on the elaboration of the two teaching methods and high and low creativity, it can be concluded that Inquiry Based Teaching is more effective to teach writing to students having high creativity. On the other hand, Guided Writing is more effective to teach writing to students having low creativity.

CONCLUSION

Based on the result of the data analysis, the research findings are IBT is more effective than Guided Writing in teaching writing for grade eighth students. It is supported by the result of the finding in which the mean score of Inquiry Based Teaching (85,45) is higher than the mean score of Guided Writing (83,82). Furthermore, the result of ANOVA test between columns showed that there is significant difference in which F_t with the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ (4.09) is lower than F_o (4.53147).

Moreover, the students who have high creativity have better writing skill than those who have low creativity for grade eighth students. It is supported by the result of the finding in which the mean score of students having high creativity (87,41) is higher than students having low creativity (81,86). In addition, the result of ANOVA test between rows showed that there is significant difference in which F_t with the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ (4.09) is lower than F_o (52,042)

Furthermore, there is an interaction between teaching methods and creativity to teach writing for grade eighth students. Based on the research findings, the effectiveness of using the teaching methods is determined by the level of students' creativity. The students having high creativity are more effectively taught using Inquiry Based Teaching, while students having low creativity are more effectively taught by using Guided Writing. The mean score of the students having high creativity taught using Inquiry Based Teaching (A_1B_1) is 89.91, while the mean score of students having high creativity taught using Guided Writing (A_2B_1) is 84.91. In addition, the mean score of

students having low creativity taught using Inquiry Based Teaching (A₁B₂) is 81, while the mean score of students having low creativity taught using Guided Writing (A₂B₂) is 82.72). Therefore, it can be finally concluded in general that Inquiry Based Teaching is an effective method to teach writing to the eighth students.

The result of the research imply that Inquiry Based Teaching relying on group learning gives different touch when Guided Writing are not effective anymore in the teaching process. Inquiry Based Teaching has been able to make students become more active to participate in the writing classroom learning. Inquiry Based Teaching as a student-centered method has changed the students' way of thinking and acting in which students as the learning agents must be aware that the learning can be successful and meaningful in the class as a result of their active involvement in that learning process. In addition, the strength of students' psychological aspects, creativity, has also affected the teaching methods to work maximally on the students in learning. This has been proved by low creative students tend to learn in passive situation with the teacher which is supposed to be more active to teach and guide the students' activities in the learning. Meanwhile, high creative students are open to student-centered learning to solve their learning difficulty and enhance their learning achievement.

Considering the HIS needs and abilities, the HIS can learn English but within their standard. Visualization plays the important role to bridge the gap on their hearing loss. Moreover, basic life skills are crucial to be taught because their parents keep feather bedding them. It blocks them to learn new things. If they never try they will never learn.

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